

TEACHING ENGLISH TO KINESTHETIC LEARNERS**Amrullayeva Maxliyo Abdurahmonovna**Tashkent Academic Lyceum No.2 of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the
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Annotation : A better knowledge and understanding of learning styles may become important as classroom sizes increase and as technological advances continue to mold the types of students entering higher education. While research in this area continues to grow, teachers should make concentrated efforts to teach in a multi-style fashion that both reaches the greatest extent of students in a given class and challenges all students to grow as learners. It is very important to understand and explore each individual's learning style.

Keywords: non-verbal communication, lesson, distance, facial expression, gestures, emotion.

People who have a kinesthetic learning style often struggle learning through traditional means and sedentary activities, like lectures and conferences. Their minds simply can't make the connection that they're doing something when listening or observing.

Kinesthetic learners have just one of many learning styles teacher come across, but they often need a little extra help. The class suits all learning styles by adding a few special activities that are fun for everyone.

These students love to learn through action and don't respond well to traditional teaching methods.

Study tips for kinesthetic learners

- Study for short (but intense) periods - 50 minutes at max.
- Sit on a ball rather than a chair when studying at home (this keeps the body constantly in action).
- Underline or highlight as you read - or at least follow along with your finger.
- Cover the page below where you are reading if you are reading dense text.
- Make up actions to memorize new information - perform skits with study partners to remember poetry, history facts, plays, etc.
- For math or science, do many practice problems to be sure you understand.
- Try walking or bouncing a basketball, etc. while reciting information.

- Write brainstormed ideas for essays on individual cards so that you can move them around to decide where to put them in the essay.
- Create an outline of a chapter as you are reading it - maybe in cartoon form.
- Write ideas on a gigantic piece of paper or white board with many colours to keep yourself very physical while brainstorming or reviewing notes.
- Check if it's possible for assignments to be completed in project form (for example a PowerPoint presentation of an essay rather than a written essay).
- For spelling practice, try acting out the letters with your body, or drawing them with a chopstick (or your finger) in a pan of rice.
- Keep a stress ball in your pocket to squeeze during class to help you maintain focus.

Kinesthetic learners are often the students who just don't get what you're trying to teach in a traditional lecture or worksheet based lesson. Kinesthetic learners take in information best when they use their whole bodies to complete practice exercises. Tactile learners are also physical learners, but they are more likely to learn things from model building and hands on instruction.

Interestingly, there was a study done in the late 1980s (Reid, 1987) that found the self-reported preference among English Language Learners for language lessons was Tactile/Kinesthetic by a wide margin. This just goes to show how important it is to try and integrate more physical and experiential elements into our English lessons.

Look for games that involve whole body responses, or have the students touching and moving things around as part of the game activity. Games with these elements are associating physical activity and touch with specific meanings. They can be divided into three broad groups: Touch Games, Spatial Games, and Craft Games.

Touch Games

The most common games involving touch are those based around having real items inside a bag, so that students have to touch the items and then perform certain tasks. These tasks are what differentiate the level of difficulty. The easiest version simply has students identify the objects that they touch in the bag. This is often a vocabulary game. To make it more difficult, the students have to describe what they are feeling, while the rest of the class tries to guess what it is.

Spatial Games

These games involve rearranging items or people and can be both kinesthetic and tactile. They include traditional games like charades and less traditional games, like Population Punctuation, where all but one person in class has a card with words or punctuation on it and the one person who is 'it' tries to arrange the people at the front of the class so that the cards make a correctly punctuated sentence using as many people as possible.

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